

HOT-DRAWING OF FIBER (FILAMENT) REINFORCED

METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

A controlled temperature metal-drawing process is used to consolidate continuous fiber (filament) reinforced metal-matrix composite wire preforms into uniaxial reinforced composite bars. The resultant processed composite structures consist of continuous and discontinuous fiber (filament) segments in a metal-matrix. During controlled temperature drawing the continuous reinforcements are loaded mainly in tension, the direction of maximum fiber (filament) strength. Thus, little fiber (filament) damage and composite interface debonding occurs during the consolidation process since buckling stresses within the structure are minimized. The manner of loading appears to break some of the continuous reinforcements at natural weak points, resulting in discontinuous fibers (filaments). Drawing aligns broken reinforcements axially and, due to hydrostatic consolidation forces imposed on each composite volume element as it passes through the die, matrix material flows into voids created where fiber (filament) ends separate. Recent work using continuous micro-reinforcements (graphite fibers) in an aluminum matrix has shown this to be the case. Graphite-aluminum composite wire preforms (35-40 v/o fibers) prepared by liquid metal infiltration of T300 polyacrylonitrile (PAN) graphite fiber tows with 6061 and 356 aluminum alloys were assembled into billets and hot-drawn at area reductions of 5 to 15 percent. Tensile tests of drawn barstock showed elastic moduli in the range of 97-138 GPa and longitudinal strengths of 717-924 MPa. Transverse strength determinations in flexure on rectangular coupons conducted for T300 G/6061 Al for both as-drawn and heat treated conditions indicated that consistently higher transverse strength values are obtained for the graphite-aluminum composite when in the heat treated condition. The longitudinal tensile strengths did not appear to be affected by heat treatment. Preliminary work on the hot-drawing of silicon carbide-aluminum wire preforms has also shown the drawing process to be applicable to the fabrication of bulk composites consisting of large macro-filaments. Metallographic examination of sections from drawn bar stock for both graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum showed the hot worked composite structures to consist of areas containing many discontinuous fiber segments. No voids or process induced defects were evident at broken fiber ends. Matrix flow occurred around fractured fiber ends effectively healing defects during consolidation. It is concluded that less damage to the composite structure occurs during fabrication, maintaining a high strength and stiffness, semicontinuous reinforced composite structure.

Introduction and Concept

A number of mechanical fabrication processes are available and have been utilized to consolidate continuous fiber (or filament) reinforced metal-matrix composites into bulk composite structural shapes. The general fabrication approach for fiber (filament) reinforced metal-matrix composites addressed herein involves the lay-up of continuous, uniaxial reinforced high strength and stiffness metal-matrix wire preforms into desired configuration(s) to which pressure and temperature, over a predetermined time interval, is applied. Diffusion bonding of the individual wire elements into a bulk composite shape or form is achieved through this processing. The composite wire elements usually consist of high strength and stiffness yet relatively brittle, low strain to failure micro (fibers) or macro (filaments) reinforcements in a ductile metal-matrix. The consolidation of the composite wire preforms into fabricated shapes must be accomplished in a manner which induces minimum damage to the brittle reinforcements, maintain strong fiber (filament) to matrix interfaces and achieve high integrity wire to wire bonds in the fabricated bulk composite. Effective stress transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement fibers or filaments must be maintained in the processed composite bulk structure, if high mechanical properties are to be achieved for the fabricated shape.

Mechanical processes commonly used for the fabrication of fiber (filament) reinforced metal-matrix composites are hot pressing and hot isostatic pressing (HIP). Mechanical hot pressing by far has obtained the most success in fabricating plates, panels and similar structures of high properties. Hot isostatic pressing (HIP) has been used for the fabrication of more complex structures such as cylinders, tubes, etc. Other mechanical working processes have been applied to the fabrication of these composites with limited success, among them notably, extrusion and rolling.

Property degradation during fabrication can be minimized through adjustment of the process parameters (pressure, temperature, and time) and by consideration of degree and type of deformation imposed upon the composite wire elements during consolidation. Processes which induce homogeneous deformation, approaching isostatic application and distribution of consolidation forces, results in less mechanical damage to the composite structure during processing, and thus can be expected to translate higher composite properties, than processes which inherently apply more severe deformations during fabrication. Low mechanical properties often observed for fabricated bulk shapes are thought to occur primarily because composite interfaces and bonds within the matrix/fiber (filament) structure are mechanically damaged by severe non-homogeneous deformations. The mechanical degradation of composite interfaces results in poor bonds and thus only limited load transfer from matrix to the fiber (filament) reinforcement can be achieved. For example, extrusion of uniaxial reinforced metal-matrix composites, induces severe damage to fiber/matrix interfaces during consolidation. Buckling stresses imposed upon the composite structure during loading, separates interfaces and severely fragmentates reinforcements. Voids and other process induced defects are introduced. A high degree of mechanical damage to the composite structure results, with accompanying degradation of properties.

In this paper a hot-drawing process is discussed which has recently received active development for the fabrication of uniaxial fiber (filament) reinforced metal-matrix shapes. The process has allowed the fabrication of simple shapes with considerably less overall matrix deformation and fiber damage, as attested by good mechanical property translations, from high strength/stiffness composite preforms to fabricated shape. Hot-drawing loads the uniaxial reinforcements in axial tension; the direction of maximum strength. As a result, minimum fiber (filament) and interface damage occurs

FIGURE 2

TABLE 1

TYPICAL T300 GRAPHITE FIBER PROPERTIES

FIBER DESIGNATION	TENSILE STRENGTH ($\times 10^3$ psi)	ELASTIC TENSILE MODULUS ($\times 10^6$ psi)	FILAMENTS	FILAMENT DIAMETER
T300 ⁽¹⁾ (PAN)	360 (2482 MPa)	34 (234 GPa)	6000	8×10^{-4} cm

NOTE: (1) UNION CARBIDE CORPORATION

TABLE 2

TYPICAL MATRIX PROPERTIES

ALLOY DESIGNATION	NOMINAL COMPOSITION (WEIGHT PERCENT)					TENSILE STRENGTH ($\times 10^3$ psi)
	Si	Mg	Cu	Cr	Al	
356 ⁽³⁾	7.0	0.3	0.2	----	Ba1	25 ⁽¹⁾ (172 MPa) 38 ⁽²⁾ (262 MPa)
6061 ⁽³⁾	0.6	1.0	0.25	0.20	Ba1	18 ⁽¹⁾ (124 MPa) 45 ⁽²⁾ (310 MPa)

NOTE: (1) AS CAST
(2) HEAT TREATED
(3) ELASTIC MODULUS OF AL ALLOYS APPROXIMATELY 10^6 psi (69 GPa)

vapor, the zinc being continually extracted from the coating step of the process as zinc chloride gas. The coated fibers are infiltrated by pulling through a molten aluminum alloy bath producing a unidirectional graphite-aluminum composite wire (Figure 2). By modification of process parameters both rayon (ex. T50) and polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based (ex. HMS, T300)

graphite-aluminum wire preforms of high mechanical properties⁽³⁾ can be prepared in this manner. Properties for the T300 (PAN) graphite fiber used in this work are given in Table 1 while the characteristics of the matrix alloys with which the fiber tows were infiltrated are shown in Table 2. Figure 3 shows a typical transverse section of 35 v/o T300 graphite fiber tow infiltrated with aluminum alloy.

FIGURE 3

Transverse

100x

Typical properties of T300 G/6061 Al and T300 G/356 Al composite wire preforms prepared for this investigation are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3

T300 (PAN) GRAPHITE-ALUMINUM WIRE PREFORM PROPERTIES

Composite System	Volume % Fiber	Wire Tensile Strength ($\times 10^3$ psi)	Wire Tensile Modulus ($\times 10^6$ psi)
T300 G/6061 Al	35 - 40	150 - 185 (1034 - 1276 MPa)	16 - 20 (110 - 138 GPa)
T300 G/356 Al	35 - 40	160 - 190 (1103 - 1310 MPa)	14 - 20 (96.5 - 138 GPa)

(b) Silicon Carbide-Aluminum

A limited quantity of silicon carbide-aluminum preforms were prepared by a continuous casting process. Continuous SiC filaments (see Table 4) obtained from Berghof (Germany) were cast into a close-packed seven-filament wire preform (Figure 4).

The casting of SiC/6061 Al wire was accomplished by pulling continuous SiC filaments of close-packed array, through a 6061 aluminum alloy melt, using a suitable designed crucible and casting die (Figure 5).

TABLE 4
TYPICAL (BERGHOF) SILICON CARBIDE FILAMENT PROPERTIES

AVERAGE TENSILE STRENGTH ($\times 10^3$ psi)	TENSILE MODULUS ($\times 10^6$ psi)	FILAMENT DIAMETER (in.)
470-500 (3241-3447 MPa)	63 (434 GPa)	0.004 (0.010 cm)

FIGURE 4
SEVEN FILAMENT SILICON CARBIDE-ALUMINUM
WIRE PREFORM

Transverse

250x

SiC is wetted by aluminum alloys at elevated liquid metal temperatures, thus no prior coating is required. The residence time is of the order of fractions of a second, which coupled with the inherent chemical stability of SiC, minimizes filament degradation due to contact with liquid aluminum. Limited volume percent control of the SiC/Al wire was obtained by variation of temperature, pull speed, and packing density of filaments. This preliminary attempt at casting SiC/Al wire preforms for hot-drawing resulted in a wire preform of approximately 70 v/o SiC. Volume percent SiC was adjusted to 40-50 v/o SiC during bar fabrication by the introduction of 6061 aluminum foils to the billet lay-up. The preparation of SiC/Al wire preforms by casting has not been optimized. Tensile modulus for these preforms has been measured at 42 msi (289.6 GPa) or approximately 92% rule-of-mixture.

General Description of Hot-Drawing Process

Hot-drawing of graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum uniaxial fiber/filament reinforced bar stock was accomplished on a modified 10 ton pull capacity draw bench. The equipment has the capacity for fabricating round cross-sections up to 5 cm in diameter to approximately 0.95 cm diameter.

Lengths of approximately 2.5 meters can be accommodated. Modifications to the equipment to allow consolidation of fiber reinforced composites include a controlled, constant temperature, die and billet preheat furnace having a maximum temperature capability of 1205°C. A die extension allows the furnace to envelope the die and billet. The billet consists of assembled fiber (or filament) metal-matrix preforms (wire) sealed in a tubular container having a long, reduced diameter, front leader (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6
ASSEMBLY OF DRAWING BILLET

A mechanical pump is attached to the tubular leader to evacuate the billet during processing. The die extension is preheated by the die furnace to the process temperature. The billet is inserted by guiding the reduced leader through the die which positions the billet in the preheat section of the furnace. A general view of the process setup is shown in Figure 7. Once in position, the billet is evacuated (vacuum pressure ~ 0.1 Torr) and then allowed to heat up to the processing temperature along with the die. It remains at temperature for approximately 30 minutes to allow outgassing of volatiles in the container. The billet is then drawn through the die at a rate of 5 cm/sec. The consolidated billet is cooled and two axial cuts are made 180° apart through the billet container wall, freeing the composite bar.

FIGURE 7

Results and Discussion

Hot-drawing trials on graphite-aluminum were performed in the solid state. The processing temperature was $504^\circ\text{C} + 12^\circ\text{C}$ for both 6061 and 356 graphite-aluminum composites, below the matrix solidus temperatures of 582°C and 557°C , respectively. Consolidation was achieved at a drawing rate of ~ 5 cm/sec. Preliminary drawing trials to establish basic process conditions for graphite-aluminum were conducted using available wire preforms. Results of these trials determined workable containment and die size combinations to subsequently hot-draw the composite systems under investigation (i.e., T300 G/356 Al and T300 G/6061 Al) with minimum material loss due to containment failures. It was concluded from these trials that a hot-working range between 0% and 15% reduction in area should be investigated to result in successful hot-drawing of graphite-aluminum for evaluation.

Billets for T300 G/6061 Al and T300 G/356 Al hot drawing runs were set up based on the trial and error results of the preliminary trials. Using 1.9 cm OD x .089 cm wall billet containment and a 1.34 cm diameter die, T300 G/6061 Al composite round bars, having nominal dimensions of 1.14 cm diameter by 30.5 cm long, were hot-drawn at 5, 10, and 15% reductions. Also, T300 G/356 Al bars were consolidated at 5 and 15% reductions using the same containment and die combination as for the T300 G/6061 Al bars. Figure 8 illustrates a typical bar fabricated by hot-drawing. Percent area reductions which billets received was controlled by amount of preform material (wires) introduced into drawing container.

Tensile specimens were machined from each 30.5 cm long x 1.14 cm diameter bar. Figures 9 and 10 are stress-strain curves obtained for single strand (6000 filament) T300 G/6061 Al at 5 and 15% reductions, respectively.

FIGURE 8
HOT-DRAWN COMPOSITE BAR

FIGURE 9

The T300 G/6061 Al series of curves (Figure 9) shows a high UTS of 924 MPa at 5% RA and a low of 814 MPa at 15% RA. It is evident from this data that the lower the percent reduction in area, the higher the ultimate tensile strength and strain-to-failure with little change in the primary (124-138 GPa) or secondary moduli (approximately 103 GPa). The higher strength at lower percent reductions is also evident in the T300 G/356 Al series of curves (i.e., a high UTS of 793 MPa at 5% RA and a low UTS or 717 MPa at 15%, Figure 10). The T300 G/6061 Al composite consistently yielded higher ultimate tensile strength values than the T300 G/356 Al at all reductions. The highest tensile strength values obtained were 924 MPa for T300 G/6061 Al as compared to 793 MPa for T300 G/356 Al, both at 5% RA. Table 5 summarizes these results.

Examination of transverse strength data determined in flexure on T300 G/6061 Al rectangular coupons machined from bars, generally indicated higher

FIGURE 10

TYPICAL STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF T300 G/356 A1 PULTRUDED COMPOSITE BAR STOCK

TABLE 5

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HOT-DRAWN GRAPHITE-ALUMINUM BARS

Trial No.	Material	Fiber Volume Percent (v/o)	Percent Reduction (% RA)	Ultimate Tensile Strength		Elastic Modulus		Flexural Transverse Strength ⁽³⁾	
				(ksi)	(MPa)	Primary E ₁ (msi)	Secondary E ₂ (GPa)	(ksi)	(MPa)
145	T300 G ⁽¹⁾ /356 A1	40	15	104	717	16.8	115.8	15.0	103.4
149	T300 G ⁽¹⁾ /6061 A1	40	15	106 118	731 814	---	---	---	---
148	T300 G ⁽¹⁾ /6061 A1	40	10	130 126	896 869	17.9	123.4	15.2	104.8
146	T300 G ⁽¹⁾ /356 A1	40	5	106 115	731 793	19.8	136.5	14.7	101.4
147	T300 G ⁽¹⁾ /6061 A1	40	5	134 130	924 896	16.2	111.7	15.6	100.7
150	T300 G ⁽²⁾ /6061 A1 (AS DRAWN)	35	5	111	765	15.5	106.9	14.4	99.3
150	T300 G ⁽²⁾ /6061 A1 (T6 HEAT TREATED)	35	5	111	765	14.3	98.6	---	---

NOTE:
 (1) Single Strand Good Filament Graphite Filament Tow.
 (2) Wire Preform Consisted of Three Strands of 6000 Filaments Each.
 (3) Values Represent Averages of At Least Two Determinations.

transverse strengths for 5% RA bars than for the 10% and 15% reductions. Average values of 43.1 MPa at 5% vs. 28.3 MPa and 32.4 MPa at 10% and 15% RA, respectively, were observed. This trend is consistent with the higher tensile strengths observed previously at 5% RA (Table 5). In an attempt to improve the transverse strength of the T300 G/6061 A1 composite bars, additional aluminum was effectively added to the composite structure by hot-drawing round bars from a lower volume percent graphite-aluminum preform. This preform consisted of three 6000 filament tows, rather than a single tow, resulting in a 35 v/o wire with an average UTS of 1034 MPa. Increasing the aluminum network throughout the composite structure and heat treating

for the composite matrix (to a standard 6061-T6 condition) was thought to strengthen the fiber composite in the transverse direction, due to the isotropic strength contribution of the aluminum matrix. Tensile and flexural transverse strengths were determined for both as hot-drawn and T6 heat treated conditions on bars fabricated in the above described manner. As indicated in Table 5 an ultimate tensile strength of 765 MPa and a modulus of 125-127 GPa were obtained for both bar conditions at the lower volume percent fiber. This indicates that the uniaxial strength and stiffness of the composite bars is primarily a function of the fiber volume percent and not affected by heat treatment. Comparison of average transverse strengths in the as-drawn vs. drawn and T6 heat treated conditions, however, showed an average strength increase from 32.4 MPa to 50.3 MPa, respectively. The heat treated strengths were consistently higher and tended to accumulate towards the high end of the transverse strength range for graphite-aluminum than values obtained for as-drawn bars. The increase in flexural transverse strength noted on heat treatment indicates that improvements in transverse strength may be realized for lower volume percent fiber composites by extending the continuous aluminum matrix network throughout the composite structure. This enables the aluminum matrix (in the heat treated condition) to contribute its

FIGURE 11

TYPICAL HOT-DRAWN GRAPHITE-ALUMINUM MICROSTRUCTURES

Transverse

(a)

250x

Longitudinal

(b)

1000x

isotropic strength in the transverse direction of the composite. Since increasing the volume percent aluminum, to increase the transverse strengths, lowers the longitudinal properties, a predetermined balance between longi-

tudinal tensile and transverse strength will be required for particular applications.

Preliminary trials were also performed on hot-drawing silicon carbide-aluminum wire preforms into bar shapes. It was of interest to determine the fabrication behavior and hot-drawing applicability utilizing large macro-filaments (SiC diameter, 1.06×10^{-2} cm) in comparison to graphite micro-filaments (diameter, 8×10^{-4} cm).

The SiC-6061 Al wire preforms produced by continuous casting were assembled into billets and hot-drawn to nominal .762 cm and 1.27 cm diameter bars. Hot-drawing temperatures were chosen to assure matrix flow around large filaments (6061 Al, $T_s = 582^\circ\text{C}$). Each 7 filament wire preform contained approximately 70 v/o SiC. To increase volume percent aluminum in the fabricated bars, extra aluminum matrix was added by introduction of 6061 aluminum foil. Groups of ten SiC-6061 Al preform wires were wrapped with sufficient 6061 Al foil and assembled, into a billet for hot-drawing to obtain a volume percent in the fabricated bar between 40 and 50%. This lay-up resulted in a SiC filament distribution consisting of densely packed regions separated by an aluminum matrix network. Mechanical properties have not been determined for drawn SiC-Al bars.

Examination of metallographic sections from consolidated graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum round bars at various percent reductions indicated that sound composite structures are achieved by hot-drawing (Figure 11 and Figure 12, respectively).

FIGURE 12

TYPICAL HOT-DRAWN SILICON CARBIDE-ALUMINUM MICROSTRUCTURES

Transverse

(a)

50x

Longitudinal

(b)

80x

In fact, at high magnifications it is evident that even around the smallest discontinuities, matrix flow has occurred and filled-in (i.e., healed) the broken ends of fibers and filaments. This observation is very significant since it shows both micro and macro fibrous reinforced composites can withstand a significant amount of hot-working and deformation with minimum composite structural damage. This implies minimum loss of composite mechanical properties during drawing fabrication as demonstrated for graphite-aluminum (and anticipated for silicon carbide-aluminum) based on structural observations.

These preliminary observations have important implications for the future fabrication and sizing of complex uniaxial fiber (or filament) reinforced structural sections, where thermal-mechanical treatment of composites becomes necessary to obtain specific engineering shapes and configurations. Additional work is planned on both graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum composites utilizing hot-drawing to fabricate angle (i.e., tee, hat, etc.) sections. A property data base must be established for such structures. Other fiber (filament) metal-matrix reinforced composites will also be investigated. The preliminary results presented herein illustrates the advantages and potential the hot-drawing process offers for fabrication of uniaxial reinforced fiber (filament) metal-matrix engineering structures.

Conclusions

1. Fabrication of uniaxial reinforced bars of graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum by hot-drawing of wire preforms, results in well consolidated bulk material with minimum damage to the composite structure. During hot-drawing, hydrostatic application of consolidation forces results in matrix flow around broken fiber (filament) ends, healing the structure.
2. High mechanical property translations have been observed from preform (wire strengths, 1034-1310 MPa) to hot-drawn fabricated shape (bar strengths, 717-924 MPa) for T300 graphite-aluminum. Similar high property translations are expected for silicon carbide-aluminum, based on microstructural observations of drawn bars.
3. Transverse strength in graphite-aluminum bars fabricated by hot-drawing can be improved by lowering the volume percent fiber in the composite and hardening the matrix by heat treatment.
4. Hot-drawing of composite preforms has potential for the fabrication of high strength and stiffness, uniaxial, micro and macro filament reinforced metal-matrix structural sections of tee, zee, hat, etc. configurations.

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